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The Work Environment, Perception and Impact on Organizational Behavior

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Abstract

The following investigation focused on studying the organizational climate, the improvement of the work environment and the performance of the collaborators that exists in the shoemaker company of the Center of the city of Villahermosa, the type of study that was included for the development of information during The research carried out was an analysis in which the observation and the qualitative study could be appreciated, as well as the implementation of interviews with the collaborators to subsequently carry out an investigation of what was observed. Within the work environment, five variables are taken into account: size, organizational structure, complexity of systems, leadership pattern, and goal directions. It was considered that the structural approach is more objective because it is based on variables that are constant within the organization and defined by management. Another factor that is of the utmost importance for the organizational climate in a company is the consideration, that is, to what extent. The employee judges his superior's behavior to be supportive or emotionally distant.

Keywords: Management, Organization, Company, Research, Organizational Climate.

Introduction

The work environment is undoubtedly one of the most important components within the administration in an organization, thanks to this element organizations can obtain a good result in terms of their objectives. Over the years this composition of words has been heard more and more,

since for organizations this can be positive or negative, including in a company the organizational climate goes beyond the work environment, that is, it means giving to be able to receive.

The organizational climate in a company can be a link or an obstacle to the performance of the worker and this is reflected both internally and externally, currently in organizations a different concept is used because some companies give importance to the human factor that works in the organization, the organizational climate is one of the determinants of the behavior of workers and the degree of satisfaction they achieve with respect to the activity they perform. Maintaining and obtaining a satisfactory organizational climate solves many future problems such as staff turnover for very short periods, poor treatment of employees towards customers and decreased productivity of the company or organization. Through the research carried out it can be seen how the departmental company of shoemaker turn analyzed has not been able to apply or develop a good organizational climate and in turn this affects the high turnover of personnel that is constantly seen for short periods of time.

The organizational climate is a phenomenon that between the factors of the organizational system and the motivational tendencies of people and groups, these translate behaviors that have consequences for the organization, such as: productivity, satisfaction, external rotation, accidents, absenteeism (González & González, 2010).

The organizational climate determines the way in which an individual perceives his work, his performance, productivity and satisfaction, contemplating the human and physical environment in which he develops. (Arteaga, 2019)

The main objective was to analyze the organizational climate for the improvement of the work environment and performance of the collaborators in the departmental company of zapaero turn of the center of the city Villahermosa Tabasco, in the same way the causes that make possible an unpleasant organizational climate were identified and the relationship between the organizational climate and job satisfaction was determined.

Methodology

The type of study that was undertaken for the development of information during the research elaborated on the company analyzed, was an inquiry in which the observation and implementation of interviews with the collaborators was appreciated, to later have carried out the development of the observed and to be able to achieve the necessary objective it was fundamental to put into practice a qualitative study in which information was collected through the observation of the company as well as Questions set to people who were within the environment or organization that was studied.

According to (Ander, 1995) the concept of techniques, in the field of scientific research, refers to the procedures and means that make methods operational (p.17)

One of the first research techniques implemented was observation, this was the main tool during the development of the research, through which most of our data was obtained that served to know the causes that make possible the problem of which possible solutions could be given. The interview was another method that was used during the development of this article, these were made to the collaborators who are part of the organization that was analyzed.

According to (Corral, 2008) the open-ended questions are:

Those in which the interviewee responds freely in his own words, are basic for exploratory interrogations, where there is no greater knowledge of the subject, the facts or the place. (p. 156)

The main choice of questions used during the research were the open questions since what was sought was to give a greater result and credibility to each question, and then develop an analysis, which was an indispensable tool to be able to know in depth the causes that made possible the bad organizational climate that exists in the analyzed company.

Development.

The organizational climate will not always be in a state of variation and this affects the organization, that is, the employee can remain within the company or can leave, but this will bring consequences whether negative or positive, the negative ones may be that the employee leaves and this will be reflected in the productivity of the organization, and the positive ones are, that the employee obtains achievements, power, satisfaction, adaptation, and innovation. That is why the organizational climate must be taken care of because from this derive many factors which will be reflected in more than one area of the company and especially in productivity or in the growth of it, without a doubt the organizational climate must be something that must not only be maintained but also take care of and develop day by day.

Within an organization the climate can also be broken down in terms of organizational structures, size of the organization, modes of communication, leadership style of management. (Constance, 2012, p. 21)

The motivation of the employee should always be to provide not only through the communication of words, but through incentives or strategies that the company proposes this in order to ensure that its employees will give their maximum in their respective areas of work, since thanks to this not only will its staff feel motivated but that the company manages to attract the attention of external people, Creating in the human factor the need to stay there for much longer and externally will achieve that there are people who want to be part of the organization.

Motivational factors involve feelings related to personal growth and development, professional recognition, self-actualization needs, increased responsibility and depend on the tasks that the individual performs in their work (Chamorro, 2014, p. 28).

Job stability should be understood as the shared responsibility of both the employer and the employee or candidate to ensure their effective participation in the work environment (Pedraza, Amaya, & Conde, 2010, p. 498).

Generally, organizational success is built with effort and dedication, and to achieve this, motivation is a concrete goal in the arduous journey to success, and this achievement causes energetic wear for the worker.

In all business organizations, managers play an important role since they are responsible for applying mechanisms that integrate and motivate their employees.

It is important to note that every business organization is responsible for creating mediating mechanisms that allow the employee to grow within the organization (Peña, 2018, p. 198).

The organizational diagnosis plays a very important role in the development of organizations since it allows analyzing and evaluating the factors that exist in them (Roa, 2004, p. 15).

The organizational climate is one of the most important components of organizations is the environment that can be developed internally and that in turn creates work and personal relationships within the dependency where it is located, this is undoubtedly one of the components that in general can not be needed in a company.

(Cornell, 1955) defines organizational climate as "a mixture of interpretations or perceptions that people make in an organization of their jobs or roles in relation to other colleagues" (p. 38). This in turn is the environment that develops among employees, this is based on the communication that exists within the group of collaborators that you have, in the relationship as well as work that exists, in the same way it is based on the values and ethics that each individual makes known in the work environment in which he is, In turn, the organizational climate not only implies the communication between employees but also influences the relationship that managers or staff with the highest category of the company has with their employees, communication is another important factor for the organizational climate to be the most pleasant since the staff with high positions are those who must have greater interaction with the staff this to create a much more comfortable. The quality of the work environment directly influences the satisfaction of workers as this is reflected in the development of the areas that each staff is in charge of and as a result there is a notable change in the productivity of the company.

The organizational climate is fundamental within an organization, it is constituted by guidelines that each worker has of himself and of the organization (Pazmiño, 2018, p. 17).

Thanks to the good organizational climate that a company executes, it can be maintained, grow and innovate in the market and this will not only be reflected in production but also in the treatment that employees offer to their customers, because a good organizational climate must be reflected internally and externally. (Forehand, 1964) "The organizational climate is multidimensional and consists of a set of characteristics that describe the organization, make it different from other organizations, are durable over time and influence the behavior of the members of the organization" (p. 361).

French and Bell diagnostic model.

This model is closely related to aspects of the organization, clearly marked and united by an administrative subsystem that is constantly interacting with the subsystems. This model has five subsystems that compose it: Technical Subsystem; Structural Subsystem; Psycho-social subsystem; Securities Subsystem; and Administrative Subsystem. (Hernández & Morales, 2016, p. 31)

Focus on individual psychological factors.

(Schneider, 1968) refers to the three processes that the individual has in the organization, highlights:

- a. The need he feels to establish social interaction, for this he seeks and selects other people;
- b. the need to establish feelings of affinity towards the organization; and
- c. Building a feeling of belonging to the organization, which can be positive or negative. (P.183-184)

It is analyzed that the psychological aspect covers the feeling and the way of rebelling of people against the characteristics of each organization, because they act according to their personal constructions of meanings in certain situations.

The psychological aspects in the construction of the meaning of the organizational climate are considered as something natural of man, in which the behavior of people at work is a product of the way they individually perceive certain factors of the work environment, which influence both at work and outside it.

At the same time, individual psychological factors are important in the measurement of the organizational climate for the impact on the functioning of the organization and need to be enhanced to try to develop those elements that can result in it being as positive as possible and that its members perceive it as favorable, which considerably influences not only the economic results of the organization, but also in the personal development of its members, an aspect sometimes forgotten, but of great weight in the work activity.

Group factor approach.

(Toro, 2005) defines climate as:

The collective and shared perception of the internal realities of the group, in which the social aspects of the task become a source of permanent satisfaction, personal growth is generated, one learns to be tolerant, to cooperate, to respect differences. This generates a climate of peace, which consequently reduces interpersonal aggressiveness, derives learning from conflicts when they occur, which benefit organizations and their members to achieve better results for society. (p. 184)

Group factors affect the organizational climate by the variables that determine it and on which individuals react by building perceptions that influence their behavior. Group factors must be taken into account in the interaction process, and their perception is the object of measurement of the organizational climate.

Likewise, (Gonçalves, 2021) that establishes "the degree of satisfaction, sense of belonging, commitment to organizational objectives, willingness to change, leadership, trust in the boss based on his consideration and support; support and trust in the group; Teamwork, also considers group and organizational factors" (p.184).

Organizational factors approach

(Ucrós & Teresa, 2010)

Each of the organizations has its own characteristics and objective properties, sometimes unique and exclusive, that affect the internal environment or organizational climate of the same, and affect the behavior of the worker, and therefore in the productivity of the company. (p. 185)

Likewise, (Rodríguez, 2005) "contemplates absenteeism and willingness to change, orientation to results and performance standards, exercise of control, organizational structure (decentralization, specialization) and communication and dissemination of policies that are of an organizational nature" (p.184).

The aforementioned organizational factors allow us to understand climate as the set of perceptions that staff form about the realities of work and organization, related to organizational policies, practices and procedures, both formal and informal.

Similarly, this approach references its analysis in the organization to indicate the difficulties and opportunities offered by the organizational system to its staff.

Communication is the most important way that every human being practices because it is by which information is exchanged daily between one individual or another, this is implemented orally and in writing and is reflected at any time. Communication in turn is based on any science such is the example of

management there must be communication to meet what the institution requires and within a company what predominates is organizational communication which is through which information is exchanged about procedures, tasks, and objectives that you want to draw or realize both internally and externally.

Thanks to the organizational communication that exists in companies, development, productivity and external and internal relations strategies are established in order to obtain the best results in human resources, in turn organizational communication allows to develop excellent forms of internal work so that they meet their objectives and be able to achieve the expected results, In the same way, maintaining excellent communication results in a good organizational climate.

Organizational communication is structured through messages. A communicative chain, whatever its length, is articulated by a series of links: the messages that occur between two subjects. It is obvious that in the organization there are many messages circulating through written or technical supports. Organizational communication is transmitted in a dyadic or serial manner. (Ansedé, 2010, p. 3)

Below is a table that shows an example of each of the approaches mentioned above, as well as possible results that would be obtained if these were put into practice.

Variable	Focus	Result
1. Morality	Psychological	Compliance with established norms and rules.
2. Behavior	Psychological	Good treatment of colleagues and customers of the company.
3. Teamwork	Group	Achievement of established objectives and goals.
4. Empathy	Group	To be able to give mutual support in different areas, in case there is an indisposition.
5. Comunicación	Organizational	Express and be heard to receive the same.
6. Growth	Organizational	Opportunities for growth in different areas and implementation of incentives.

RESULTS.

The results obtained during the search for information for the realization of this article were negative given that thanks to the research instrument that was used during the investigation it was possible to see that the organizational climate within this company is unfavorable and that communication is practically not prolonged, due to this the collaborators have saved different complaints and as a result a large turnover of personnel is obtained during the last years. Throughout the first phase of the interview applied to the employees of the company studied, the following question was applied: Do you consider yourself a fundamental part of the company where you are currently a collaborator?

As a result of this question were obtained as an answer that the collaborators if they consider that they are a fundamental part of the company since thanks to the sellers it is possible to give exit and attention to the customers who commonly frequent this company, as well as in the same way the sideboards and cashiers

gave the same answer since thanks to them it is possible a very good distribution of the products to be exhibited. In the course of the second phase of the interview, the following questions were asked: What is communication like within the company? Where as a response by the members of this organization mentioned the following: Communication within the organization varies greatly that is to say when it is required to communicate with the supervisors it is necessary to be in a fast and cutting way because they usually do as they listen to you but do not show interest in what we need to express, as for the managers and assistant managers it could be said that it is a little more fluid this also depends on the Type of character that each one has, with co-workers is somewhat difficult because it is usually complicated because if the supervisors see us talking they put us to do cleaning to avoid that any plot is put together such as theft or other examples, but I consider that there is no good communication within the company because if this were so, fewer problems could be avoided. When do you say that due to the visits of the supervisors communication is complicated to what you refer? I mean that you should avoid talking to your co-workers during the visit of the supervisors because normally they are very serious with the staff and confusion should be avoided such as thinking that you do not have a working relationship but sentimental with your colleagues and that you can also be losing customers or in the worst case that you may be planning some kind of theft towards the company, so when they see us talking they send us to clean or clean the sideboards even if we have already done it.

Thanks to these answers, credibility was given to the initial idea that communication is not developed in the analyzed company and therefore the organizational climate is not present, and in turn this is affected by the high turnover of personnel that has always existed. In the last phase of this interview, the following questions were asked, from which the same answers and complaints were obtained from the collaborators of the departmental company of shoemaking of the city of Villahermosa: Do you consider that the company treats its employees well? Most of the time this varies, for example when entering they treat you in a good way they train you one day, but with the passage of time they change that is to say times they do not respect our stipulated schedules normally they make us stay half or an hour after our departure time and this does not pay us, in the days that are called seasonal days that is in December dates they want us to enter before Our schedule and that we stay longer and sometimes we have not even gone out to eat because we practically cannot, the meal times are unfair to me because they only give us half an hour and in half an hour barely and I am arriving with my lunch, and they have also been few incomprehensible in some situations. When you mention that they are incomprehensible which you mean exactly? Once I had a very bad headache and reported to my manager that I felt bad and that if I could retire but as it was season he did not leave me and the only thing he did was give me a pill that according to was for pain but in reality I did not know if it was for pain, And also what happened to a friend when I started COVID19 she suspected that she had symptoms of this disease then notice to the manager gave permission to withdraw and to notify how it continued, a few days later my friend warned that she was positive for the virus and that she could not attend in Human Resources they told her not to worry about taking the necessary time to be able to return but It was not like that, because a few days later they warned her not to return that she was already fired and that when she improved to return for her liquidation, then according to my way of thinking I think it was wrong because she needed his support and because there were no reasons since she was alone in her area and there was no substitute

To say that it was because of the cut of the personnel, then that was a bad attitude that the company took towards this situation.

Conclusions

During the development of the research for this article it was possible to visualize the importance of the organizational climate in organizations since on more than one occasion companies have been affected by the lack of knowledge of this issue, in the company to which this research topic was applied it was observed that it lacks communication between managers and collaborators or supervisors and collaborators, Most of the time the most important thing for senior managers is that the employees of the organization comply with the established without listening to possible suggestions that promote the better functioning of these organizations, the organizational climate of this company is definitely in terrible condition, given that for a long time the situation has been the same. When we talk about organizational climate we do not mean that respect within the organization will cease to exist and that the ways to engage in conversation will be in any way, but it means the importance of knowing how to listen to your collaborators so that in turn you can not only meet the objectives and goals set but also achieve a warmer work environment, and both employees and senior managers can be heard. During the interview it could be seen that on more than one occasion they have exceeded the functions that each collaborator has as responsibility within the organization and employees are dissatisfied with this situation, not only expect respect for their days, but also that they can have a little more freedom of expression in their workplace. It was concluded that this company must know the meaning of the compound organizational climate and that it must begin to perform the functions that it determines so that its collaborators can feel comfortable during their stay and the rotation of personnel ceases to be affected because of the lack of communication that this company lacks.

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